

An In-Depth Analysis of the Life of President Ronald Reagan

Adam Ahmed, Ryan Ahmed

Introduction

With all his fiery and his might, Ronald Reagan told the Soviet Union's president, Mikhail Gorbachev, "Mr Gorbachev, tear down this wall!" With Reagan's life work, he made an impact on the world. Ronald Wilson Reagan was the 40th president of the United States of America. He served 2 terms as the Governor of California and 2 terms as the President of the United States. He was mostly known as the "Great Communicator" and "The Gipper" because Reagan spoke confidently and acted as George Gipper, a dying football player during his Hollywood years at the "Warner Brothers" after college. He was also known for the assassination attempt on him from John Hinkley Jr. He always smiled and was always happy at any cost, which is why America loved his sunny optimism. He was the man that ended the Cold War and took down the Berlin Wall in 1987. He was an important man as he saved many people and inspired others to work hard.

Life Before Politics

Ronald Reagan's father was a failed business man and was an alcoholic. This affected Reagan, as he was distant from his family. However, he always craved attention and applause. Reagan also had 22/100 vision, which meant he could not read the top of an eye chart. He could only see the radius of 1 yard. He could not catch many footballs because of this because he did

not see the ball coming towards him. In Eureka College, he played many sports such as swimming, football, and lifeguarding. He saved 77 people as a lifeguard and got paid \$15 a week. He is a true hero. Reagan got a degree in sociology and economics. He then created an economic policy named, "Reaganomics". He became student body president because he spoke and communicated very well. He went under contract for the "Warner Brothers" and starred in about 50 films. This is how he met his second wife, Nancy Davis. After college, he was hired at an Iowa radio station where he was a sportscaster. A sportscaster is somebody who talks about different sports.

In his Hollywood years, he acted in a movie where he played as George Gipp, a dying football player. Gipp's famous quote was, "Win one for the Gipper." Reagan's most important acting role was in this movie. This is how he got nicknamed "The Gipper". Reagan became deaf in the right ear because when he was in Hollywood, a gun got shot off on stage near his ear. That is why he had trouble hearing. He was also the president of the Screen Actors Guild. He got a taste of leadership from that and he spoke very well. He was the president of the SAG for 5 consecutive years. Reagan's mother was a religious woman. She prayed many times a day and she prayed for her family so much. Reagan lived in a small town in Illinois. It was called Dixon. Reagan also lived in a low-income family. His parents did not get much money when they worked. When Reagan got married to his first wife, Jane Wyman, they had 3 kids. Micheal, Christine and Maureen Reagan. And when Reagan was married to Nancy Davis, they had 2 kids. Ron Reagan and Patti Davis. In total, Reagan had 5 kids. Reagan met his second wife, Nancy Davis at the time he was with the "Warner Brothers" after college. Before getting a contract at the "Warner Brothers", he acted in school plays. He had experience from the school plays so he acted very well.

Life During Politics

Reagan made a big speech for Barry Goldwater when he was running for president. Many people saw his speech and agreed to him. He became famous from that. A couple of years later, he won against Pat Brown for the Governor of California by 1 million votes. He served 2 terms as Governor of California. After his terms, he ran for president in 1980. He won against Jimmy Carter and remained in office for 8 years. He selected George H.W. Bush as his Vice President. George H.W. Bush was the C.I.A. director. In Reagan's presidency, he nominated 5 supreme court justices. Presidents are lucky to select 1 supreme court justice but Reagan got to choose 5.

Instead of smoking, Reagan ate Jelly Belly jelly beans. Many tons of jelly beans were shipped to the White House for Reagan's presidential inauguration. In fact, Jelly Belly made a portrait for Reagan that shows Reagan. More than 10 thousand jelly beans were used to create the portrait. Ronald Reagan promised tax cuts and he did. This is how the economy grew. Reagan was shot and wounded by John Hinkley Jr. as Reagan was returning to his limousine after a speech at the Washing D.C. Hotel. After his assassination attempt, his approval rating soared. It was 69%. Reagan hated nuclear weapons. That's why he ended the cold war by signing the Intermediate Nuclear Forces Treaty in 1987. He also wanted the United States to stay armed, ready for war. When Reagan was inaugurated, he was 69 years old. He was the oldest person to go to office as president of the United States of America until Joe Biden at 78 years old in 2021. Reagan became friends with the Soviet Union's leader, Mikhail Gorbachev. He made a speech telling Gorbachev, "Mr. Gorbachev, open this gate. Mr Gorbachev, tear down this wall." Reagan's presidency lasted 8 years. Reagan also freed the hostages from the Iran Hostage Crisis

on January 20, 1981. It was the same day Reagan was inaugurated. His presidency ended a year after he gave the speech to Mikhail Gorbachev.

Conclusion

Ronald Reagan enjoyed his life after he was president. He worked in his presidential library, he lived in Los Angeles with his wife, and he traveled to many places. That fun did not last all his life though. Reagan addressed to the American people that he had alzheimers. Alzheimers is a disease where you lose memory. His alzheimers lasted for 10 years until he died on June 5th, 2004 in his California home. Alzheimers took over his life and he died. He was buried under his presidential library. From a little boy in a low-income family to the 40th president of the United States, Ronald Wilson Reagan was a true hero beyond our hearts.

Works Cited

"Reaganomics". PBS. June 10, 2004. Archived from the original on October 11, 2007. Retrieved August 21, 2007.

Meacham, John; Murr, Andrew; Clift, Eleanor; Lipper, Tamara; Breslau, Karen; Ordonez, Jennifer (June 14, 2004). "American Dreamer". *Newsweek*. Retrieved June 3, 2008.

"Anthony M. Kennedy". Supreme Court Historical Society. 1999. Archived from the original on November 3, 2007. Retrieved November 12, 2007.

"Pendleton, Clarence M. Jr". *Notable Kentucky African Americans Database*. University of Kentucky. Retrieved March 19, 2013.